

Deliverable D-JRP22-WP2.1

Workpackage WP2-T1

Responsible Partner: ANSES

Contributing partners: NVI, PIWET, FLI, BIOR, SSI, INIAV.

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JIP/JRP deliverable	D-JRP22-WP2.1 Validation of SSCT for diagnostic of E. multilocularis in fox		
Project Acronym	MEME		
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Due month of the report	36		
Actual submission month	45		
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R, Save date: 10-Sep-2121		
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU		
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/>
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Validation of Segmental Sedimentation and Counting Technique (SSCT) for diagnostic of *Echinococcus multilocularis* in fox

1. Introduction

1.1. Epidemiological context

Alveolar echinococcosis (AE) is a zoonotic parasitic disease involving canids as definitive host (mainly fox) for the adult worm stage and a broad spectrum of small rodent species as intermediate hosts for the larval stage. Humans are considered as dead-end hosts for the larval stage of this parasite. AE is considered as a severe disease of human interest with a northern hemisphere distribution caused by infection of the tapeworm *E. multilocularis* (Em). The infected definitive hosts harbours worms in their intestines, which are shedding eggs in the environment by faeces. The oral ingestion of these eggs may result in human infections.

The diagnosis of Em infection in the definitive host is important for epidemiological studies to estimate presence and prevalence of the parasite in the studied areas. Difficulties in the detection of the adult parasite in definitive hosts mainly derive from the irregular shedding of Em eggs and the inability to distinguish them morphologically from those of *Taenia* spp. Since the available diagnostic methods differ among laboratories both methodologically and in their performances, there is a need to validate and harmonize the detection methods. The SSCT was developed using the SCT (Sedimentation and counting technique) which is considered the reference method for diagnostic of Em infections in foxes by WHO (2001). The SSCT method is based on the principle of preferential distribution of Em worms in the posterior part of the small intestine in order to achieve a significant saving of analysis time but while maintaining a very high sensitivity.

1.2. References

Umhang, G., Woronoff-Rhen, N., Combes, B., & Boué, F. (2011). Segmental sedimentation and counting technique (SSCT): An adaptable method for qualitative diagnosis of *Echinococcus multilocularis* in fox intestines. *Experimental Parasitology*, 128 (1), 57-60.
WHO/OIE Manual on Echinococcosis in Humans and Animals: a Public Health Problem of Global Concern (2001). Edited by J. Eckert, M.A. Gemmell, F.X. Meslin and Z.S. Pawlowski.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Sampling of intestines

Each participant will have to collect intestines from red foxes in Em endemic areas from their country. The whole intestine (small and large intestine) need to be sampled. A decontamination period at -80°C during at least four days is required in order to prevent any risk of Em infection.

2.2. SSCT protocol

The protocol to realize the validation of the SSCT was transmitted in a SOP to each partner. Briefly, the fifth segment (posterior part) was considered to be the large intestine and removed. The small intestine was divided in four equal parts named S1 to S4 from anterior to posterior parts. Each segment has to be analysed independently for the presence of Em worms.

3. Results discussion

Among the 594 red fox intestines already collected by five partners (NVI, PIWET, FLI, ANSES, BIOR), 477 were already analysed independently for each of the four segments of intestines resulting in 120 positive samples (Table 1). Collection and analysis will be continued in order to be finished in December 2021 (M48) with the aim of obtaining more positive intestines to estimate of the sensitivity of SSCT method.

Table 1: Number of red fox intestines collected and analysed for SSCT validation by the partners.

	collected	analyzed	positive
ANSES	163	141	33
NVI	200	140	3
PIWET	100	100	57
BIOR	96	96	27
FLI	35	0	0
Total	594	477	120

The protocol of validation was also used for raccoon dogs from Poland and Latvia in order to determine a potential combination of a pair of segments providing a high sensitivity. Among the 70 intestines analysed, five were infected by Em. These data will be combined with those from experimental results previously obtained by ANSES.